

NATIONAL SOCIO-CULTURAL STEREOTYPES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

One of the fundamentals for demonstrating a new language to learners is to examine the culture of the target language. So far, several issues have been identified whenever teaching a new language has not been accompanied with teaching the new culture. This paper describes how to detect socio-cultural aspects in language classes (EFL) for teaching the culture of a new language might help educators improve the quality of their instruction. We view "cultural constituents of the target language" as a significant aspect in learning a new culture in this study. We also need to understand what "socio-cultural stereotype" entails. The technique involves exposing language learners to the culture of a new language and providing teachers with strong social and cultural pedagogical materials, followed by an analysis of the students' efficiency in class, ability to complete tasks, and amount of time saved to determine how teaching Target Culture (TC) affects learning a new language. The findings show that knowing the social and cultural elements of the target language on the one hand helps learners perceive the new language better and helps them decide how, when, and where to use target language structures on the other hand saves time.

Introduction: Standardized education resources and methods are a prime illustration of stereotyped thinking in education. Unfortunately, this includes learner stereotyping. This conventional view of the learner, as defined by Pennycook (1994:293), is that he or she is "a one-dimensional acquisition device, a sort of language learning machine."

This mindset towards the student is conventional, and it persists despite the introduction of the 'communicative method' to language teaching, with its emphasis on "learner-centeredness". In addition to LLS, personality qualities such as encountering language, encouragement, self-confidence, anxiety, and attitudes can all impact second

language learning (Gass et al., 2013). In simpler terms, the process of language acquisition incorporates individual variances in a way that influences the achievement of language learners. Brown (2007) defines stereotyping as an attitude towards the culture or language in question. Individuals' attitudes and behaviours indicate the concepts generated in their minds after communication breaks down. The reasonable and unrealistic stereotyped views that individuals are likely unaware of are the primary sources that feeds these thoughts (Dökmen, 2013).

Stereotypes are impressions and opinions about a person, nation, or culture that are frequently built incorrectly, simplified, and generalised. Furthermore, people might have stereotyped notions about a foreign language that they learn since, during the language acquisition process, people engage not just with family, instructors, and friends, but also with everything around them.

Individuals may develop erroneous judgements about language throughout this process, obstructing engagement and communication. This effects learners' attitudes and behaviours, learning methods and methodologies, and engagement during instruction in the foreign language learning process (Ünal, 2015). Stereotypes that damage efficient communication, one of the objectives of foreign language acquisition (Özden, 2018), may lead to a decline in the interests of the language studied and the cultural elements of the culture using that language. In this instance, it is unavoidable that some issues will arise as a result of decreasing the efficiency of the LLS that the learners require during the process of foreign language acquisition. In this context, it is deemed vital to clarify misconceptions about foreign languages using language learning methodologies in order to combat issues that may occur in foreign language teaching and learning.

Main part:

A genuine shift in foreign language teaching ideology is required, particularly in EFL, to one in which the preoccupation should be, as Widdowson (2003:41-42), "with English that is global in its use, and local in its learning." He goes on to argue that "The established or official position, the orthodox view, is diametrically the opposite to this, for it sees English as local in its use and global in its learning: and its monolingual teaching is assumed to be exportable as a global commodity, universally applicable, whatever the local circumstances of the learners" .

-Standardization of the commodity, in this case teaching materials, courses for potential EFL instructors, and even the language itself, is unavoidable in global marketing. The finished product is a standardized, stereotypical image of the end-users - the teachers and the learners. The identification of stereotyping in EFL teaching is not new, and many writers argue that foreign language instruction should be more diverse. Teaching techniques and materials should be tailored to the student rather than being generic. In terms of general revision, materials, measures have been done in some countries such as Spain, Italy, and Chile to 'localise' materials by having EFL classes tailored to their needs, as well as individualized additional resources in other nations produced.

-Dökmen (1997) categorises the following stereotypes as having the potential to impact a person's learning process and everyday life: Polarisation, Personalisation, Absolutism, Extreme Effort to Change, Extreme Sacrifice, Extreme Regression, and Overgeneralization. These stereotyped beliefs are characterised by resistance to change and a high likelihood of

being disregarded (Dökmen 2008). These stereotyped ideas can cause a number of difficulties for L2 learners. As a result, recognising and removing these stereotyped ideas will have a substantial impact on the language process.

-While stereotypes have been extensively researched (Gunaldo et al., 2020; Mollaeva, 2018; MacKenzie, 2018; Nikitina, 2015; Lewandowski, 2014; Nguyen & Kellogg, 2010), few studies have been developed specifically to analyse stereotypes and language acquisition practices. By identifying learners' stereotyped ideas regarding foreign languages and LLS, this study hopes to make a substantial contribution to the relevant literature. Furthermore, the pattern of relationships between foreign language learning strategies and stereotypical thoughts about foreign languages is assumed to broaden perspectives in regards to leading academics and instructors in the development of new approaches and techniques to be used in the language learning-teaching process. This study, which intends to find out whether stereotypical views take place during the foreign language process of learning and if they minimise the degree of learning strategies for learners, is thought to provide a new perspective on the problems encountered during the foreign language learning process.

-The lack of having direct interaction with a native speaker of a foreign language while studying the country of origin of the language strengthens the general educational importance of the foreign language and, as a result, a more constant encouragement for the social and cultural factors component of teaching foreign languages. Several research on this topic provided as an impetus for the formulation and application of the sociocultural component in the content of foreign language training. According to I. L. Bim, it is vital to integrate components of the linguistic culture of peoples who speak the language of study, as well as regional knowledge in connection to communication settings, in the learning material. Within the scope of this approach, we are discussing the necessity to saturate the topic matter of regional studies materials with an emphasis on cultural discussion.

-The method of Z. N. Nikitenko, which presents all of the qualities of this component, realises a sufficiently rich sociocultural component: - Language understanding of country culture (national reality and etiquette); - Speech and nonverbal behaviour skills and abilities. Without comparable and background vocabulary, the instructor must pay close attention.

They are untranslatable because they lack corresponding terms in a literal sense, and their meaning is exposed via interpretation. Holidays, transportation, and emblems are examples. Background vocabulary is made up of words whose meanings cannot be defined without a specific lexical unit binding. These terms are undoubtedly present in the thoughts of native speakers of culture and language, connected with something truly outstanding, and are frequently mentioned in conjunction with other notions. Because knowledge is not necessarily associated with actual abilities, and skills are not always particularly synonymous with competence.

As an illustration, consider the following. How to assess a person's sociocultural knowledge, skills, and competencies if he has the right to be known as a connoisseur of a particular culture, can answer any question related to history, art, legal norms without any preparation etc., in many countries around the globe.

-Analysing the distinctive features of nations in various areas, select connections and demonstrate particulars of their development in a specific historical period, and make an

economic as well as social predicted for the future; adhering to chauvinistic principles and is forceful towards those who do not agree with his ideas about right and wrong, norms of behaviour, and life.

Every subject helps to create a comprehensive view of the world. Learners, but from a unique perspective. Because it is a tool for interaction and cognition, the subject "foreign language" plays a unique function in the moulding of pupils' overall worldview; it is both linguistic and A sociocultural view of the world. The topic's specificity "foreign language" is one of the most important components of foreign language instruction material. Language is not the foundation of science, and their activities include: learning, reading, writing, listening, and speaking are all distinct types of BPD activities.

Another aspect of foreign language instruction is that mastering speech activities are only feasible through communication (oral or written). Students learning socio-cultural literacy must complete a variety of difficult activities, and it is critical in both psychological and educational aspects to make these tasks particularly relevant to them.

Conclusion:

It has been shown in the study papers that language learners' perceptions about a target language nation impact their desire to acquire a foreign language (L2 motivation). Educational academics have rekindled their interest in preconceptions about a target language (TL) nation, its culture, and individuals that language learners bring into the classroom. It has been acknowledged that language learners' images and stereotypes of a TL country play an important role in motivating or discouraging them to engage in the process of language learning, and calls have been made to investigate the relationships between these stereotypes and language learning motivation. However, such investigations are still few.

The socio-cultural component of foreign language teaching on which knowledge of realities, customs, and traditions of the country of the studied language is formed; knowledge and skills of communicative behaviour in acts of speech communication; skills and abilities of verbal and nonverbal behaviour are included in the content of national culture. The socio-cultural component of foreign language curriculum has considerable potential for engaging students in cross-cultural discourse and acquaintance with national cultural achievements in the formation of universal culture.

The socio-cultural component of English language teaching content has enormous potential for achieving tangible qualitative results in developing foreign language communication, and for implementing the strategic aim of foreign language teaching as the development of students' ability to intercultural communication.

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